

MECHANISM OF THE POLYMERISATION OF THIOCYANOGEN FROM MAGNETIC STANDPOINT.

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Mechanism of the polymerisation of thiocyanogen to para form has been investigated by studying the paramagnetic property in different solvents e.g. carbon disulphide, bromoform and cyclohexane of different concentrations.

Thiocyanogen was obtained in the free state by Soderback (*Annalen*, 1919, **419**, 217) by the interaction of iodine with an ethereal suspension of silver thiocyanate. Lecher and Goebel (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 2223) determined by cryoscopic method the molecular weight of thiocyanogen in bromoform. Solutions less than half normal indicated thiocyanogen to be dissolved as $(\text{SCN})_2$ but those with higher concentrations gave evidence of polymerisation. When a solution of thiocyanogen in solvents such as carbon disulphide, cyclohexane, bromoform etc. is left for sometime, a brick-red or an orange amorphous mass separates, which is the polymeric form of thiocyanogen known as 'para thiocyanogen'.

The polymerisation of thiocyanogen to the para form can proceed through various stages represented either by (SCN) , $(\text{SCN})_2$, $(\text{SCN})_3$, $(\text{SCN})_4$, $(\text{SCN})_5$, $(\text{SCN})_6$,..... $(\text{SCN})_n$ or by $(\text{SCN})_2$, $(\text{SCN})_4$, $(\text{SCN})_6$, $(\text{SCN})_8$, $(\text{SCN})_n$ where n is an even integer i.e. through the stages containing molecules having both even and odd numbers of electrons or those having only even number of electrons. The life period of different stages during the course of polymerisation is very short, therefore, methods such as depression in freezing point, elevation of boiling point, etc., cannot be employed with success to explain the mechanism of polymerisation.

Molecules containing odd number of electrons exhibit paramagnetism, whereas those with even number of electrons exhibit diamagnetism. Now, if the polymerisation of thiocyanogen proceeds through the formation of odd molecules, the solution of thiocyanogen at times would exhibit paramagnetism. Therefore the authors in the present investigation have undertaken to investigate the mechanism of polymerisation of thiocyanogen to para form by studying the magnetic property of thiocyanogen in different solvents.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Thiocyanogen in carbon disulphide, bromoform and *cyclohexane* was prepared by the interaction of silver sulphocyanide and bromine dissolved in these solvents. Pure solvents available from the stores were further purified by the usual methods. Pure bromine was prepared by Scott's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 848), traces of moisture present in it were removed by redistilling it over fused calcium bromide. In each solvent solutions of various concentrations were prepared. The maximum concentrations studied are indicated in Table I. When higher concentrations were prepared, thiocyanogen started polymerising into the insoluble form immediately. Deposition of the para form was quickest in bromoform and less so in carbon disulphide and *cyclohexane* respectively.

TABLE I.

Limits of concentration of thiocyanogen for the various solvents.

Carbon disulphide	0.48 N
Bromoform	0.33
<i>cycloHexane</i>	Very low.

Concentration of thiocyanogen was determined by allowing a known volume of the solution to react with excess of KI solution and titrating the liberated iodine against standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

The susceptibilities of the solutions were found on Guoy type balance (*Compt. rend.*, 1889, 109, 935; *cf.* also Bhatnagar, Mathur and Kapur, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1928 3, 153) and were checked on Decker magnetic balance (*cf.* Bhatnagar, Nevgi and Tuli, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1935, 9, 311). The susceptibility of thiocyanogen in solution was calculated from the relation

$$\chi_{\text{thiocyanogen}} = \frac{\chi_{\text{soln.}} - (1 - p/100)\chi_{\text{solvent}}}{p/100}$$

where p represents the weight of thiocyanogen in 100 g. of the solution. If left to evaporate all the solutions eventually deposited the orange, insoluble para thiocyanogen which was diamagnetic. The results of the various measurements are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen from fresh solutions in carbon disulphide.

Temp. = 18°.

No.	Colour.	Density.	Normality.	% SCN.	$\chi_{\text{soln.}}$	Susceptibility Specific.	Mol.
	Colourless	1.270	0	0	-5.500×10^{-7}	—	—
1.	Light yellow	1.278	0.48	1.19%	-5.476	-4.42×10^{-7}	-57.28×10^{-6}
2.	„	1.276	0.42	1.92	-5.480	-4.21	-48.84
3.	„	1.274	0.40	1.82	-5.459	-3.25	-38.70
4.	„	1.274	0.39	1.77	-5.461	-2.96	-34.74

TABLE III.

Magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen from carbon disulphide.

Solutions kept for 24 hours.

Temp. = 20°.

No.	Colour.	Density.	Normality.	% SCN.	$\chi_{\text{soln.}}$	Sp. Susceptibility.
1.	Light yellow	1.273	0.082	0.37%	-5.251×10^{-7}	$+6.18 \times 10^{-7}$
2.	„	1.273	0.076	0.35	-5.341	+4.00
3.	„	1.272	0.060	0.27	-5.421	+2.51

TABLE IV.

Magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen from solutions in bromoform.

Temp. = 20°.

No.	Colour.	Density.	Normality.	% SCN.	$\chi_{\text{soln.}}$	Susceptibility Sp.	Mol.
	Colourless	2.888	0	0	3.160×10^{-7}	—	—
1.	Yellow	2.815	0.33	0.679%	3.158	-0.410×10^{-6}	-47.56×10^{-6}
2.	„	2.820	0.31	0.638	3.165	-0.410	-47.56
3.	„	2.832	0.25	0.513	3.166	-0.410	-47.56

TABLE V.

Magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen from solutions in cyclohexane.

Temp. = 20°.

No.	Colour.	Density.	Normality.	%SCN.	$\chi_{\text{soln.}}$	$\chi_{\text{thiocyanogen}}$
—	Colourless	0.7750	0	0	8.100×10^{-7}	
1.	Red	0.7751	0.02 to 0.03	0.25	8.052	$+1.08 \times 10^{-6}$
2.	„	0.7750	„	0.24	8.053	+1.17
3.	„	0.7750	„	0.24	8.033	+2.00

TABLE VI.

Magnetic susceptibility and density of the orange para form as obtained from different solvents.

Temp. = 20°

Solvent.	Density.	χ .
Carbon disulphide	1.753	3.36×10^{-7}
cycloHexane	1.755	3.35
Bromoform	1.762	3.36
		Mean 3.36×10^{-7}

DISCUSSION.

From the results tabulated above, the following points are brought out in prominence:

1. In bromoform solutions with concentrations below 0.5N, thiocyanogen exhibits a constant specific magnetic susceptibility of -0.410×10^{-6} .

2. In fresh carbon disulphide solution (Table II) of concentration 0.48N and 0.42N the specific magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen is -0.442×10^{-6} and -0.421×10^{-6} respectively, and in solutions of lower concentrations the value decreases. Furthermore, when these solutions are kept overnight, there is a decrease in the concentration due to separation of the insoluble para form and the thiocyanogen then exhibits paramagnetism (Table III).

3. The *cyclohexane* solutions are dull red in colour and in spite of the great dilution of the solution, thiocyanogen shows definite paramagnetism (Table V).

4. The specific magnetic susceptibility values and the density measurements of para thiocyanogen as obtained from different solvents show them to be similar in nature.

Kauffmann and Kogler (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 178) found that thiocyanogen polymerises with the formation of cyanogen thiocyanate and dithiocyanogen monosulphide, and therefore they assumed that this halogenoid is capable of existing in two tautomeric forms to which they assigned the following structural formulae :

Brindley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, 11, 786), Kido (*Sci. Reports Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 1), Bhatnagar and Lakra (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1933, 8, 43) and many others have found that Slater's method of calculating charge distribution gives magnetic susceptibilities in better agreement with experiment than those calculated according to Pauling's method.

When the molecular magnetic susceptibility values for formulae (I) and (II) are calculated by taking into account Slater's values for gram ionic susceptibility of sulphur and Pascal's corrected values for carbon and nitrogen and constitutive correction factor due to each $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ group, we get the molecular susceptibility of (I) by the additivity law to be -45.90×10^{-6} and for the molecular susceptibility of (II), -64.79×10^{-6} .

Slater's gram-ionic susceptibilities.

S^{-2}	S^2	S^4
-34.36×10^{-6}	-12.15×10^{-6}	-5.73×10^{-6}

Pascal's corrected values of susceptibilities.

	$\times 10^{-6}$
Carbon	-6.00×10^{-6}
Nitrogen	-5.57
Constitutive correction factor for $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$	9.77

The molecular weight of thiocyanogen in bromoform was determined by Lecher and Goebel (*loc. cit.*). Cryoscopic measurements for solutions less than half normal indicated thiocyanogen to exist as $(\text{SCN})_2$. As given in Table IV, the specific magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen is -0.410×10^{-6} , and assuming it to exist in the form $(\text{SCN})_2$, its molecular susceptibility comes out to be $-0.410 \times 116 \times 10^{-6}$ or -47.56×10^{-6} .

Comparing the value -47.56×10^{-6} obtained above for thiocyanogen with -45.90×10^{-6} and -64.79×10^{-6} , the values for the two tautomeric forms of thiocyanogen calculated on the Slater's basis, it is clear that in bromoform solutions, less than semi-normal, thiocyanogen exists as $(\text{SCN})_2$. Taking Slater's values to be correct, the percentage of the two tautomers in bromoform solutions works out as (I) = 91.21% and (II) = 8.79%.

Further, because the value of molecular susceptibility lies between those of the two tautomeric forms of $(\text{SCN})_2$, it is evident that in these solutions thiocyanogen does not ionise to give the free radical SCN. These results are in accord with the cryoscopic determinations of Lecher and Goebel (*loc. cit.*).

The values of molecular magnetic susceptibility of thiocyanogen calculated from freshly prepared 0.48N and 0.42N solutions in carbon disulphide (Table II) come out to be -51.28×10^{-6} and -48.84×10^{-6} respectively. These values are higher than the values obtained from bromoform solution as well as those calculated for the formula $\text{N} \equiv \text{C} - \text{S} - \text{S} - \text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ (Slater), but less than that calculated for the formula (II).

It is clear from these results that in solutions of concentration 0.42N and higher, thiocyanogen shows tendency to tautomerise between formula (I) and (II) and there is 71.5 and 84.4% of (I) in solution of 0.48 and 0.42 normality respectively.

However, the values of molecular susceptibility obtained for slightly more dilute solutions (Table II) are even less than the calculated value for formula (I). This decrease in the value shows that in the fresh dilute solutions, thiocyanogen ionises to give the odd molecules SCN, which being paramagnetic reduce the diamagnetism of the dimolecular form appreciably.

The Bohr magneton value for an odd molecule calculated from the formula $2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M (T - \theta)}$ comes out to be 1.73. Taking θ to be zero for approximation and $T = 293^\circ \text{A}$, the χ_M for a free radical from the equation $1.73 = 2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M \times 293}$ comes out to be 1272×10^{-6} .

In case of thiocyanogen the free radical SCN has a molecular weight 58. Specific susceptibility calculated from $\chi_M = 1272 \times 10^{-6}$ for this free radical would be 21.93×10^{-6} . The specific magnetic susceptibility of $(\text{SCN})_2$ as found in bromoform solution is -0.410×10^{-6} . Assuming the solution of

thiocyanogen in carbon disulphide to be a mixture of SCN and (SCN)₂ and calculating on this basis the percentage of free radical SCN in carbon disulphide solution of normality 0.40 and 0.39 would be as given in Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Solvent	Normality.	χ .	Free radical.
CS ₂	0.40	-0.325×10^{-6}	0.38%
CS ₂	0.39	-0.296	0.51

When the fresh solutions in carbon disulphide were kept overnight an orange polymer separated out as insoluble deposit and the magnetic susceptibility of the filtered solution exhibited paramagnetism (Table III). The paramagnetic specific susceptibility of thiocyanogen varied from 0.618 to 0.251×10^{-6} for solutions of concentration 0.082 to 0.060*N* respectively. These results show that the polymerisation of thiocyanogen to para form takes place through the various stages represented by SCN, (SCN)₂, (SCN)₃, (SCN)₄, (SCN)₅,.....(SCN)_{*n*}, and not through (SCN)₂, (SCN)₄, (SCN)₆,.....(SCN)_{*n*} where *n* is an even integer. So that when the solution has an excess of the odd molecules, it exhibits greater paramagnetism than when the concentration of the even molecules is greater. The susceptibility values found out are the net results of these opposing factors.

Solutions of thiocyanogen were also prepared in cyclohexane. Although the concentrations of thiocyanogen were low (0.03*N*) yet one striking feature noticed in their case was that the solutions were dull red in colour and thiocyanogen was definitely paramagnetic in nature. The colour of the solution, coupled with the definite paramagnetic values obtained for thiocyanogen clearly shows that in these solutions of thiocyanogen there is an appreciable amount of the free radical SCN present. The percentage of the free radical SCN as calculated is given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.

Solvent.	Thiocyanogen in the solution.	$\chi_{\text{thiocyanogen}}$.	Free radical SCN.
cycloHexane	0.25%	1.08×10^{-6}	6.67%
„	0.24	1.17	7.07
„	0.24	2.00	10.78

When the solutions of thiocyanogen in various solvents were made to stand for more than 48 hours, all of them deposited an orange coloured

para form. The density measurements of the various samples and the magnetic susceptibility values as given in Table VI show that except for slight variation due to experimental error, the samples are the same in nature. As regards the constitution of this para form nothing is known. Its molecular weight had not been determined due to various difficulties such as its total insolubility in various solvents and decomposition on heating.

Farquharson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 219) has found that when cyanogen chloride $\text{Cl}-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ polymerises to $(\text{CNCl})_n$ with the replacement of triple bonds by double bonds, the molecular susceptibility of cyanogen chloride polymer decreases.

According to Pascal the bond constitutive effects are

so that the disappearance of three $(-\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ bonds should raise the diamagnetic value of susceptibility by 2.4 and the appearance of 3 $(-\text{C}=\text{N}-)$ bonds should lower it by 24.6, so that there should be a net decrease of 22.2.

During the polymerisation of thiocyanogen the value of specific magnetic susceptibility has fallen from -0.410×10^{-6} in bromoform solution to -0.336×10^{-6} for the para form (Table VI). This fall can be due to the replacement of some of the triple bonds by the double bonds as in the case of cyanogen chloride studied by Farquharson. It may be suggested that the para form may have a structure resembling in some way the structure of polymerised cyanogen chloride.